

Toksavé: Culture Talks is a podcast that is a series of interviews with people who have personal and cultural connections with the PARADISEC archive.

It was launched in 2019 as part of the UN International Year of Indigenous Languages.

“Toksavé” is a Melanesian (Pacific) pidgin word which means information such as a public notice, advertising or explaining something to your target audience.

Music and Language are central to cultural identity and heritage for Indigenous people and communities. The podcast contributes to cultural continuity through sharing Indigenous knowledge, opening up the archives and promoting community outreach.

Produced by Jodie Kell & Steven Gagau

16 episodes covering 10 regions across Oceania

Archival Loop

- **Empowering Indigenous Voices**

Valuing Indigenous people as experts and recognising them as custodians of their own cultural knowledge.

- **Connection and Reconnection**

Making archival materials accessible to enable the sharing of knowledge and lived experiences of cultural practices.

- **Building Relationships**

Prioritising respectful intercultural relationships to ensure cultural safety, accountability and value for long term impact.

- **Enlivening the Archive**

Bridging archives, communities and researchers inspires storytelling and song, cultural revitalisation and the transmission of intergenerational knowledge.

Follow this link to access the Toksavé Culture Talks podcast episodes

Empowering Indigenous Voices

Episode 14: PNG: Central Province Music and Dance

Collections: MC1, IC1, PC2

A community initiative by the PNG Peroveta Singers of Canberra responding to archival collections with song and dance.

Peroveta (Prophet Songs)

Sene Cultural Dance (Kitoro)

Connection and Reconnection

Episode 15: Ngali nuts: work songs and delicacies in Malaita, Solomon Islands

Collections: IF01

Community elder engaging with a researcher on his 1970s audio recordings and sharing cultural practices and music of Ngali nuts harvesting.

Ngali nut cracking in Malaita, 1969

Jodie Kell, Ian Frazer, Mary Sattin, Steven Gagau

Building Relationships

Episode 2: Rabaul, PNG: The Researcher and the Tolai

Collections: MW6, TCT1

A long term collaboration between a researcher and an archivist who is also a community member from the originating place of research, an insider-outsider perspective.

Michael Webb & Steven Gagau

Rabaul

Johnny Obed

Cultural significance of sharks

Enlivening the Archive

Episode 9: Paama, Vanuatu, Sharks and shark spirits

Collections: SD1, TCT1

Much like weaving a basket, a community member weaves stories inspired by archival materials to bring them to life.

